

Hand grip strength and functional status of persons living with HIV/AIDS

Chidozie Emmanuel Mbada^{1 A-F}, Olaniyi Onayemi^{2 A-F}, Omotade Israel Tosin^{1 A-F}, Stanley Monday Maduagwu^{3 A-F}, Olubusola Esther Johnson^{1 A-F}, Christopher Olusanjo Akosile^{4 A-F}, Makinde Moses Oluwatosin^{1 A-F}

¹ Department of Medical Rehabilitation, College of Health Sciences, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile – Ife, Nigeria

² Department of Dermatology and Veneriology, Faculty of Clinical Sciences, College of Health Sciences, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile – Ife, Nigeria

³ Department of Physiotherapy, University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Maiduguri, Nigeria

⁴ Department of Medical Rehabilitation, College of Health Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi Campus, Anambra State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Objective: Long-term use of Highly Active Antiretroviral Therapy (HAART) among Persons Living with HIV/AIDS (PLWH) is associated with muscle wasting and weakness, and disability. Hand Grip Strength (HGS) assessment may help monitor myopathies and functional status in PLWH. This study compared HGS and Activities of Daily Living (ADL) between PLWH and apparently healthy controls. **Methods:** One hundred and fifteen consecutive (46 PLWHs and 69 apparently healthy controls) individuals participated in this study. Homogeneity among PLWH was based on physician's diagnosis of clinical stage-1 HIV. HGS was assessed using Camry Electronic Hand Dynamometer. Basic and instrumental ADL was measured using Barthel Index and Functional Activities Questionnaire respectively. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Alpha level was set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** The control group had significantly higher mean values for weight and body mass index ($p < 0.05$). The PLWHs had significantly lower HGS compared with the healthy controls with poorer mean values recorded among the women groups ($p < 0.05$). PLWHs had higher level of dependence in basic and instrumental ADL ($p < 0.05$) with 20% requiring minimal assistance in ADL. There was no significant correlation between HGS and each of ADL, IADL, CD4 Count ($p > 0.05$). **Conclusion:** Hand grip strength was significantly poorer among PLWHs, especially, females. ADL measures was not significant different between persons with HIV/AIDS. However, some PLWHs having some level of dependence in tasks of daily living bowels, bladder, toilet use and requires minor help transfer. However, HGS was not significantly correlated with both basic and instrumental ADL and CD4 Count.

Keywords: Hand grip strength, Functional status, HIV/AIDS, Nigeria

Introduction

The pandemic of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV)/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) has led to serious health and socioeconomic challenges for more than two decades [1]. HIV causes severe damage and eventual destruction of the immune system by causing the DNA of CD4+ cells to replicate itself [2]. On the other hand, AIDS refers to the most advanced stage of HIV infection, defined by the occurrence of any of more than 20 opportunistic infections or HIV –related cancers [3]. The presence of HIV/AIDS as well as its symptoms and complications are associated with physiological and psychosocial impairments and high mortality [4-7].

The introduction of combined anti-retroviral therapy known as HAART has led to a major reduction in mortality and morbidity [8,9] and improvement in the wellbeing of People Living with HIV/AIDS (PLWH) [10].

HAART is based on two major families of drugs, inhibitors of reverse transcriptase, which can be either Nucleoside-analog Reverse-Transcriptase Inhibitors (NRTIs) or non-nucleoside analogues, and protease inhibitors (PIs) [8, 9]. However, adherent to HAART is very difficult because of toxicity, as its long-term use is associated with several secondary effects [8, 9]. HAART often causes muscle damage (myopathy) which often manifests itself as wasting and weakness. It is hypothesized that NRTI can interfere with mitochondrial DNA synthesis, which in turn leads to high levels of lactate and lactic acidosis, liver steatosis, peripheral neuropathy, lipatrophy and myopathy [11, 12].

Consequently, the HAART induced myopathies is a major pathologic progression often observed in skeletal muscle due to a primary abnormality of the muscle fiber itself [13-15] and it results in muscle weakness which is a

clinical expression of frailty [16, 17]. Frailty involves declines in physiologic complexity or reserve in other systems, leading to loss of homeostatic capability to withstand stressors and resulting vulnerabilities. Frailty has been considered synonymous with disability, comorbidity, and other characteristics [18]. Disability is commonly expressed as experiencing difficulty in carrying out tasks usually classified as activities of Daily Living (ADL) and/or Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL) [19, 20]. ADL functions are essential for an individual's self-care (e.g., dressing and feeding yourself), whereas IADL functions are more concerned with self-reliant functioning in a given environment (e.g., making the beds and shopping) [21, 22]. Even though advancing HIV/AIDS leads to frailty and disability, less study have assessed ADL and IADL in this population [23, 24].

Hand Grip Strength (HGS) assessments have been used in many studies especially in the elderly to evaluate functional ability and frailty [23, 24]. Also, HGS can be used as a measure of degree of myopathy as characterized by muscle weakness [16, 17]. Although, PLWHs are faced with significant disability and frailty especially in the advance stages [11], there is a paucity of studies on HGS assessment among them. Assessment of HGS in PLWH may help to monitor the level of myopathy even in the asymptomatic stage of HIV/AIDS. In addition, assessment of the relationship between HGS and ADL in PLWH on HAART may have diagnostic and prognostic values. Therefore, this study assessed HGS and activities of daily living (ADL and IADL) in PLWH and their healthy controls.

Materials and Methods

One hundred and fifteen consecutive (46 PLWH and 69 apparently healthy control) participants were recruited into this case-control study. The PLWH comprised of 14 (30.4%) males and 32 (69.6%) females while the healthy controls were made up of 40 (58.0%) males and 29 (42.0%) females. The PLWHs in this study were a homogenous HIV-infected individuals in clinical stage-1 who were on HAART at the Virology Research Clinic of the Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex, Ile-Ife, Nigeria (OAUTHC). The control group were self-reported sero-negative individuals. Volunteers for the control group were excluded if they were less than 18 years or were relatives or careers of the PLWHs.

Approval for this study was granted by the Ethics and Research Committee of the OAUTHC. The Virology Research Clinic, OAUTHC gave permission for the study to be conducted at the centre. Each participant gave informed consent to participate in the study. Clinical characteristics (for PLWH only) and socio-demographic variables of the participants were obtained using a self-developed proforma. Anthropometric variables compris-

ing weight, height and BMI were also measured. A weighing scale (Inters Ikea BV) calibrated from 0-120kg was used to measure the body weight to the nearest 1.0kg. Height was measured with a height meter (HM210D) in centimeters (cm) with the participants standing with shoe-off on the height meter platform while looking straight. A straight ruler was placed on the vertex of the head and the corresponding value was recorded. Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated as the ratio of weight (Kg) to Height squared i.e. $BMI (kgm^{-2}) = \frac{Weight(kg)}{height(m)^2}$.

Basic and Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (ADL) was measured using the Barthel Index (BI) and the Functional Activities Questionnaire (FAQ) respectively. Completion of both questionnaires took between 5-8 minutes for each participant. The original BI was designed to measure 10 areas of basic ADL related to functional independence or dependence in mobility and self-care tasks involving wheelchair to bed transfer, personal toilet, toilet transfer, bathing, walking, stair climbing, dressing and bladder and bowel control [25]. The original BI uses an ordinal scale scoring system ranging from 0 to 100 points in 5-point increments. A score closer to 100 indicates increased functionality whereas scores closer to 0 represent increased dependency [25]. Since its development, the BI has been employed as a measure of functional status among various patient groups and also as an outcome tool to assess treatment effectiveness [26-29].

Functional Activities Questionnaire as a measure of instrumental ADL covers participants' performance on 10 separate categories of IADLs. These are, 1) writing checks, paying bills, keeping financial records; 2) assembling tax or business records; 3) shopping alone; 4) playing a game of skill; 5) making coffee or tea; 6) preparing a balanced meal; 7) keeping track of current events; 8) attending to and understanding a television program, book, or magazine; 9) remembering appointments, family occasions, medications; and 10) traveling out of the neighborhood. Performance in each category was rated as follows: 0-normal; 1- has difficulty, but does it by self; 2- require assistance; or 3- dependent. Overall, FAQ performance was evaluated using two separate methods: total FAQ score and average score across FAQ items. FAQ is considered a suitable instrument for acute and primary care, home and rehabilitation settings, as well as for research [30].

Hand grip dynamometer (Camry Electronic Hand Dynamometer, 90 KG/200 Lbs) was used to assess HGS of participants. In measuring HGS, the participant was made to sit on a straight-back and armless chair of standard height with the test arm held at 90° elbow flexion position and the forearm in neutral position without radial deviation. The hand was positioned parallel to

the forearm holding the dynamometer. Participant was instructed to squeeze maximally and hold until the reading is taken. Two measurements were taken for the dominant hand and the average value was recorded. For standardization, the dynamometer was set at the second handle position. No verbal encouragement was given [31].

Data Analysis: Data was summarized using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Inferential statistics of Independent t-test was used to compare HGS, ADL and IADL of PLWH and healthy controls by gender and generally. Pearson's moment correlation analysis was used to analyze the correlation between HGS and each of ADL, IADL, CD4 count and general characteristics of PLWH but without CD4 count in healthy controls. SPSS version 16.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) for windows was used for statistical analysis. The alpha (α) level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Computations: Barthel Index functional status classification: "independent", score of 80–100; "minimal assistance", score of 60–79; "partially dependent", score of 40–59; "very dependent", score of 20–39; and "totally dependent", score of 0–19 [26, 27].

Results

Table 1 shows the general characteristics of the PLWHs and controls by gender. The control group had significantly higher mean values for weight and body mass index ($p < 0.05$). Comparison of HGS, ADL and IADL between the PLWH and controls is shown in tables 2. The mean HGS for PLWH was significantly lower compared with the control group ($p > 0.05$). The frequency distribution on BADL between PLWH and controls is presented in table 3. Overall, based on Bifunctional status classifications, 80% of the PLWH were functionally independent while 20% requires minimal assistance. Table 4 shows the frequency distribution of IADL. From the result, level of dependence of PLWH was higher compared to the healthy control. The result of the Pearson's product moment correlation analysis between HGS and each of ADL, IADL, CD4 Count and general characteristics of the participants is presented in table 5. There was no significant correlation between HGS and each of ADL, IADL, and CD4 count among the PLWH and control group respectively ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

This study compared HGS and activities of daily living (BADL and IADL) between stage-1 PLWHs on HAART and the apparently healthy controls. The findings of the study shows that anthropometric variables (i.e. weight and BMI) and HGS of the PLWH were significantly lower than that of the healthy controls. Despite, the beneficial effect of the use of HAART, studies have shown that

PLWHs frequently lose weight and strength. Apart from the direct effect of long-term HIV infection, leading to the release of cytokines and cellular damage which in turn increases energy expenditure, decreases nutritional intake and alters intestinal absorption [32]; HAART itself has toxic and deleterious effects on the muscular system [8, 9, 11, 12]. HAART often causes muscle damage which often manifests itself as wasting and weakness [33, 34]. Muscle weakness and wasting is often caused by damage to the mitochondria, energy-regulating organelle, that have their own DNA. Nucleoside analogs, the backbone of AIDS drug 'cocktails' are notorious for damage of DNA [12]. Hence, HGS can be used as a measure of degree of myopathy which characterized by muscle weakness [16, 17].

Hand grip strength test is considered a good indicator of frailty and strong predictor of mortality [31, 35]. In addition, HGS is considered an important index of physical function among PLWH [36–38]. However, only few studies have assessed HGS in PLWH. The results of the available studies are consistent with this study's finding on poor HGS among PLWHs [38–40]. The finding of this study also revealed a gender predilection to poorer HGS among women in both PLWH and control groups. It is added that the direct effects of HIV-infection on muscles, in addition to the negative side effects of HAART may account for the significant lower HGS in PLWHs compared with their healthy control. Furthermore, HGS tends to decline with lower lean body mass, increased systemic inflammation, and increased central fat distribution [41]. Given that chronic inflammation and abnormalities in fat distribution are common in HIV-infected persons and contribute to morbidity and mortality, even among persons receiving effective therapy [42, 43], these factors could potentially contribute to the frailty and concomitant functional decline observed in HIV-infected populations. Some investigators have implicated tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α) and its receptors, interleukin (IL)-6, and C-reactive protein (CRP) with sarcopenia and decreased grip strength [41, 44].

This study found comparable level of BADL between PLWHs and the healthy controls without gender bias. From this study, 80% of the PLWH in this study were considered functionally independent while 20% require minimal assistance. The PLWHs had some level of dependence in tasks of daily living involving bowels, bladder, toilet use and transfers. Also, the findings on IADL shows that PLWHs have limitations ranging from having difficulty to being dependent in tasks involving writing checks and paying bills or keeping financial records, assembling tax records, business affairs or papers, preparing a balanced meal, keeping track of current events, paying attention to, understanding, or discussing a TV program, book or magazine, travelling out of the neighborhood,

driving or arranging to the buses. Despite, that the PLWHs in this study were homogenously stage-1 (asymptomatic) individuals, there was still evidence of limitation in physical function among them. This finding confirms some-previous studies that have shown that HIV/AIDS generally influence ADL [45-47]. Similarly, HIV infection has been reported to have a propensity to produce a great variety of disabling conditions, and functional disability is generally the patient's primary problem [48, 49]. Literature reports that the most common manifestation leading to disability in PLWHs was weakness and chronic fatigue, which often prevents them from continuing vocational activities, hobbies, and self-care [47, 50]. Also, IADL such as financial management, purchase of groceries, cooking, using transport, shopping, managing medication and planning social activities have been reported to be impaired [51]. Therefore, evaluation of functional status and disability among individuals with HIV/AIDS is recommended [27, 40, 46, 52].

Furthermore, there is need to investigate the link between HIV-related physical impairment and frailty measures. As a result, this study investigated the correlation between HGS and activities of daily living. However, the finding of this study revealed no significant correlation between HGS and each ADL and IADL. Unfortunately, there is dearth of studies reporting correlations between HGS and activities of daily living, therefore, making comparison of this study's findings difficult. Nonetheless, it is opined that this study's findings on the correlation be-

tween HGS and activities of daily living may be different if carried out among PLWH in symptomatic stages. Therefore, the findings of this study may have limited external validity to PLWH in other clinical stages. Although, PLWHs in the asymptomatic stage often, are yet to have severe physical function and functional status impairment, however, clinicians can employ use of HGS and activities of daily living measures as diagnostic and prognostic tools for physical impairment in HIV/AIDS and as a rehabilitation outcome tool. The validity of the result of this study will be strengthened by other studies and among other clinical stages of HIV/AIDS.

Conclusion

Hand grip strength was significantly poorer among PLWH compared with the healthy controls with female PLWH having much poorer HGS. ADL measures, though different but was not statistically significant between both groups with some of the PLWH having some level of dependence in tasks of daily living bowels, bladder, toilet use and requires minor help transfer. However, HGS was not significantly correlated with both basic and instrumental ADL and CD4 Count.

Table 1: Independent t-test comparison of general characteristics between PLWH and healthy controls and by gender

Variable	PLWH Group				Control Group				PLWH Group (n=46)	Control Group (n=69)	t-cal	p-value
	Male (n=14)	Female (n=32)	t-cal	p-value	Male (n=40)	Female (n=29)	t-cal	p-value				
	X±SD	X±SD			X±SD	X±SD						
Age	43.4±7.24	39.0±1.86	1.439	0.157	36.5±12.7	45.4±10.5	-2.763	0.007	40.3±9.79	39.1±12.7	-1.577	0.118
Height	1.73±0.08	1.60±0.07	5.245	0.001*	1.69±0.09	1.56±0.07	5.545	0.001*	1.64±9.79	1.65±0.10	7.064	0.001*
Weight	62.9±16.2	60.8±16.0	0.410	0.684	71.9±12.0	74.2±20.3	-0.578	0.566	61.5±16.0	72.5±14.8	1.310	0.193
BMI	21.0±4.92	23.5±5.32	-1.528	0.134	25.3±3.90	30.3±7.24	-3.729	0.001*	22.8±5.29	26.7±5.54	-1.701	0.092

Key: BMI = Body Mass Index
* indicate significant difference

Table 2: Independent t-test comparison of HGS, ADL and IADL of PLWH and Healthy Controls by gender

Variable	PLWH Group				Control Group				PLWH Group (n=46)	Control Group (n=69)	t-cal	p-value
	Male (n=14)	Female (n=32)	t-cal	p-value	Male (n=40)	Female (n=29)	t-cal	p-value				
	X±SD	X±SD			X±SD	X±SD						
HGS	59.8±18.0	21.5±7.06	10.49	0.001*	67.1±17.9	31.2±11.2	8.329	0.001*	33.2±21.1	56.7±23.0	14.40	0.001*
BADL	19.4±1.45	19.4±1.24	-0.043	0.966	20.0±0.01	19.9±0.45	1.582	0.118	19.4±1.29	20.0±0.24	1.710	0.090
IADL	2.14±4.38	3.38±4.52	-0.858	0.395	0.01±0.01 ^a	0.01±0.01 ^a	0.001	0.001*	3.00±4.47	0.01±0.01	-2.771	0.007*
CD4 Count	4.76±180	5.02±259	-0.344	0.733								

Key: HGS = Hand Grip Strength; BADL = Basic Activities of Daily Living; IADL= Instrumental Activities of Daily Living
* indicate significant difference

Table3: Percentage distribution on responses on Basic Activities of Daily Living items

SN	Item	PLWH Group	Control Group
1	Bowels		
	0 = incontinent (or needs to be given enemata)	0	0
	1 = occasional accident (once/week)	15.2	0
	2 = continent	84.8	100
2	Bladder		
	0 = incontinent, or catheterized and unable to manage	0	0
	1 = occasional accident (max. once per 24 hours)	19.6	0
	2 = continent (for over 7 days)	80.4	100
3	Grooming		
	0 = needs help with personal care	0	0
	1 = independent face/hair/teeth/shaving (implements provided)	100	100
4	Toilet use		
	0 = dependent	0	0
	1 = needs some help, but can do something alone	10.9	0
	2 = independent (on and off, dressing, wiping)	89.1	100
5	Feeding		
	0 = unable	0	0
	1 = needs help cutting, spreading butter, etc.	0	0
	2 = independent (food provided within reach)	100	100
6	Transfer		
	0 = unable - no sitting balance	0	0
	1 = major help (one or two people, physical), can sit	0	0
	2 = minor help (verbal or physical)	6.52	0
	3 = independent	93.4	100
7	Mobility		
	0 = immobile	0	0
	1 = wheelchair independent, including corners, etc.	0	0
	2 = walks with help of one person (verbal or physical)	0	0
	3 = independent (but may use any aid, e.g., stick)	100	100
8	Dressing		
	0 = dependent	0	0
	1 = needs help, but can do about half unaided	0	0
	2 = independent (including buttons, zips, laces, etc.)	100	100
9	Stairs		
	0 = unable	0	0
	1 = needs help (verbal, physical, carrying aid)	2.17	1.45
	2 = independent up and down	97.8	98.5
10	Bathing		
	0 = dependent	0	0
	1 = independent (or in shower)	100	100

Table 4: Percentage distribution on responses on Instrumental Activities of Daily Living items

SN	Item	Not applicable/Normal	Has difficulty but does it by myself	Requires assistance	Dependent
		PLWH (Control)	PLWH (Control)	PLWH (Control)	PLWH (Control)
1	Writing checks and paying bills or keeping financial records	71.7 (100)	19.6 (0)	8.7 (0)	0 (0)
2	Assembling tax records, business affairs or papers	71.7 (100)	13.0 (0)	2.1(0)	13.0(0)
3	Shopping alone for clothes, household necessities or groceries	100 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
4	Playing a game of skill or working on a hobby	91.3 (100)	8.7 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
5	Heating water, making a cup of coffee or turning off the stove	100 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
6	Preparing a balanced meal	69.6 (100)	17.4 (0)	2.17 (0)	10.9 (0)
7	Keeping track of current events	76.1 (100)	15.2 (0)	4.35 (0)	4.35 (0)
8	Paying attention to, understanding, or discussing a TV program, book or magazine	73.9 (100)	13.0 (0)	4.35 (0)	8.7 (0)
9	Remembering appointments, family occasions, holiday and medication	100 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
10	Travelling out of the neighborhood, driving or arranging to the buses	67.4 (100)	17.4 (0)	4.35 (0)	10.9 (0)

Table 5: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation among HGS and each of ADL, IADL, CD4 Count and general characteristics of the participants

Variable	PLWH Group	Control Group
	r(p)	r(p)
BADL	-0.020 (0.893)	0.179(0.141)
IADL	-0.083(0.584)	a
Age	0.194(0.197)	-0.420(0.001)**
Height	0.594(0.001)**	0.720(0.001)**
Weight	0.201(0.181)	0.048 (0.697)
BMI	0.067(0.658)	-0.827(0.001)**
CD-4 Count	0.058(0.700)	

Key: HGS = Hand Grip Strength; BADL = Basic Activities of Daily Living; IADL= Instrumental Activities of Daily Living; BMI= Body Mass Index; HT= Height; WT= Weight.

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

a. Cannot be computed because at least one of the variables is constant.

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Corresponding Author:

Address:

Dr. Chidozie E. Mbada
Department of Medical Rehabilitation
College of Health Sciences
ObafemiAwolowo University
Ile-Ife, Nigeria

Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.